

CITIZEN SCIENCE AND THE DISSOLUTION OF INEQUALITIES IN SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

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Representation in civic and scientific epistemologies

(i) Political parties and movements increasingly criticize democratic institutions for strong biases and elitist structures, arguing that the governance of stakeholders and experts undermines democratic values.

Both phenomena are expressions of a more general problem that politics faces: a lack of public representation in civic and scientific epistemologies.

(ii) At the same time, not only the democratic institutions but also academia and the practices of scientific knowledge production are problematized: a larger public is questioning scientific authority and expertise.

Civic and scientific epistemologies have to negotiate the same constituting decisions: They need to decide whom they consider as speakers and which politics they follow.

Agency as analytical category in digital, participatory knowledge practices

Citizen Science aims to be a democratic way of knowledge production, integrating scientists and non-scientists into the research process, offering the opportunity to represent a broader public in scientific knowledge production.

If citizen scientists act as sensors or data collectors e.g. by counting birds, the participation is utilized in a predefined hierarchy and without inclusion of individual expertise. In contrast, citizen scientists who analyse and interpret texts, bring their own perspective into the analysis.

It is therefore not only important to enable participation, but to discuss how power is distributed between the participants. The degree of agency given to the participants in Citizen Science projects is crucial for their representation in knowledge production.

The symmetry between civic and scientific epistemologies offers the means to distinguish between democratic and post-democratic practices in science.

In order to be democratic, it is crucial that in citizen science participants gain agency, meaning that they are included equally without predefined hierarchies and with their individual expertise.